

Technical Paper:

Evaluation of non-proportional multi-axial stress states in drive-train components related to contacts

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Estimating the fatigue strength of multiaxially loaded components using current standards has shortcomings for certain stress conditions. Therefore, different methods to estimate the severity of non-proportionality of load cases are investigated. First, four integral-based calculation methods of a non-proportionality factor are analysed on a simple plane stress load case. Their spatial capabilities are then tested for contact on an example of a shaft-hub shrink fit model. Qualitative two of the four selected methods perform well for this type of loading. Consequently, the basis for subsequent quantitative fatigue analyses with experimental validation has been prepared.

Keywords: multi-axial fatigue, non-proportionality, stress state analysis, contact stresses evaluation

INTRODUCTION

In all areas of engineering, relevant standards and guidelines form the basis for the design of components and component contacts. Particularly in the field of drive technology, calculations of highly dynamic systems with complex stress conditions emerge. Although current standards and guidelines (e.g. FKM guideline [1] or DIN 743 [2]) provide calculation bases for shaft-hub connections, these only use simplified methods that abstract the complicated local stress situation. Both guidelines enable a local strength verification, often using additional calculation algorithms (e.g. FE method). In most cases, the correction factors derived here relate to the maximum occurring stress amplitudes or critical load spectra. In the field of drive technology in particular, however, there is a superposition of differently composed stress curves. The resulting effect of the non-proportional stresses on the multi-axiality has not yet been taken into account [1, 2]. Depending on the material and type of load, this can lead to a reduction in strength and thus reduce the lifespan of the analysed components, as shown by Sonsino et. al. [3] and Hassan and Kyriakides [4], as well as Susmel [5].

Based on these findings, adjustment formulae were developed by Itoh et. al. [6] and Fesich [7], which enable the implementation of a correction factor for multiaxiality in the calculation methods. The factor K' is described here as an adjusted parameter, which is based on the material parameter α and the degree of non-proportionality of the load f_{NP} , the so-called non-proportionality factor. The parameters K and K' can be selected as strength parameters of the guidelines, equivalent stresses or equivalent strains, depending on the specific situation, see Riess et. al. [8].

$$K' = (1 \pm \alpha f_{NP})K \quad (1)$$

The sign in front of the relationship refers to the application in each case, as a safety factor $K < 1$ or a utilisation factor $K > 1$ is calculated depending on the application. Without the influence of the material (i.e. $\alpha = 1$), a value range between 0 to 1 results for f_{NP} , whereby $f_{NP} = 0$ corresponds to a proportional load case.

At this point it should be mentioned that the evaluation of non-proportionality always involves a transient stress state $\sigma(t)$. Thus, an independent temporal change of the stress components is possible.

There are various approaches for defining f_{NP} . One major group is based on the critical plane method. Well-known representatives of this group are the works of Fesich [7], Kanazawa et. al. [8], Papuga [10] as well as Skibicki and Sempruch [11]. What they all have in common is that before this method can be used, the critical component cross-sections must be defined in order to determine a critical plane. For a discrete system, this means that for each element n and each time t , a complete rotation of the intersection plane over two Euler angles must be performed in order to determine the most critical value of f_{NP} Susmel [12].

In order to reduce the calculation intensity, methods have been developed that directly take into account the temporal course of the stress tensor. For example, Chu et. al. [13] show for the plane case that an enclosing ellipse of the stress path in the σ - τ coordinate system can be used to describe the non-proportionality of the stress state. The non-proportionality factor f_{NP} is calculated according to Eq. (2) on the basis of the main axis ratio of the ellipse. The smaller of the two main axes in the numerator must always be selected with $h < w$. Here h defines the height and w the width of the ellipse.

$$f_{NP,chu} = h/w \quad (2)$$

Many other envelope shapes can be selected in this way to determine the non-proportionality, e.g. Chen et. al. [14] or [10]. However, the application of this method fails for three-dimensional stress tensors or requires significant adjustments, which is why no further attention is paid to them. Nevertheless, this idea forms the basis for further formulations of non-proportionality, which have been extended to the spatial stress case relevant for contacts. Bishop [15] and Gaier et. al. [16] use the area

moment of inertia of the stress trajectory instead of an enclosing form in stress space. To account for any stress components, the resulting tensor of moments of inertia is treated in R^6 space. This is achieved by transforming the stress tensor from $\sigma(t) \rightarrow R^6$. The shear stresses are provided with a pre-factor $\sqrt{2}$ in order to achieve coordinate invariance. The reason for this lies in the symmetry of the stress tensor. In [15], *Bishop* describes a numerical algorithm to implement the calculation. With reference to [15], the following equations are given:

$$L = \sum_{k=1}^N L^k \quad (3)$$

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{2L} \sum_{k=1}^N L^k (x^{k+1} + x^k) \quad (4)$$

$$I_{ij} = \frac{1}{6} \sum_{k=1}^N L^k [y_i^k y_j^k + y_i^{k+1} y_j^{k+1} + (y_i^k + y_i^{k+1})(y_j^k + y_j^{k+1})] \quad (5)$$

where $L^k = \|\mathbf{x}^{(k+1)} - \mathbf{x}^k\|$, $\mathbf{x}^k = \mathbf{x}(t_k)$ describes the distance between two points. Afterwards the mean value corrected stress component $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{x} - \bar{\mathbf{x}}$ is used for further calculations. The non-proportionality is determined as the ratio of the maximum eigenvalues of the inertia tensor. Thus, an eigenvalue along the first-principal axis a_1 can be determined for each timestep t . Similar to equation (6) the next smaller value along a_j can be determined.

$$a = \max_{t \in [a,b]} \{\|a_1(t)\|\} \quad (6)$$

$$b = \max_{t \in [a,b]} \{\|a_i(t)\|\}, i = 2 \dots 6 \quad (7)$$

$$f_{NP,bishop} = \sqrt{\frac{b}{a}} \quad (8)$$

A variation of the presented approach is given by *Gaier* [16]. While the calculation still uses the R^6 space the definition of the evaluation values is changed. It must be emphasised that no mean stress correction happens in this calculation.

$$I_{ii} = \sum_{k=1}^N \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^6 S_j^2(t_k), i = 1 \dots 6 \quad (9)$$

$$I_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^N S_i(t_k) \cdot S_j(t_k), i, j = 1 \dots 6, i \neq j \quad (10)$$

The determination of the non-proportionality factor is inverted in comparison to *Bishop* so that the following applies to the eigenvalue consideration:

$$f_{NP,gaier} = \sqrt{\frac{I_6}{I_5}} \quad (11)$$

A significantly different method is proposed by

Bolchoun et. al. [17]. Here, the proportionality of the load is to be estimated on the basis of the correlation of the transient behaviour of the stress components. *Cor* describes the correlation coefficient between two stress components. A correlation of 1 or -1 for σ_x and τ_{xy} would describe a proportional stress state. The formulation can be regarded as spatial, as the correlation is integrated over the angles θ and ψ and finally minimised over ξ . The angular limits of the integrals and the minimisation operator are to be equated with a spatial rotation, which seeks the weakest correlation of the normal and shear stress.

$$M = \min_{\xi \in [0, \pi]} \int_{-\frac{\pi}{2}}^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \int_0^{2\pi} Cor^2(\sigma_x, \tau_{xy}) d\theta d\psi \quad (12)$$

$$f_{NP,bolchoun} = 1 - M \quad (13)$$

The last non-proportionality factor analysed here was formulated by *Itoh* et. al. [18]. *Itoh* describes the non-proportionality as the deviation of the maximum principal stress S_1 at time t from the maximum amplitude of the principal stress $S_{1,max}$. The time at which the maximum stress occurs is referred to as t_0 .

$$S_1(t) = |S_1(t)| = \max[|S_1(t)|, |S_2(t)|, |S_3(t)|] \quad (14)$$

$$S_{1,max}(t_0) = \max[S_1(t)] \quad (15)$$

The non-proportionality factor is then described as the curve integral of the absolute maximum principal stress $S_1(t)$ and the deviation of the resulting vector \mathbf{e}_R from the initial vector \mathbf{e}_I .

$$f_{NP,itoth} = \frac{\pi}{2S_{1,max}L_{path}} \int_C |\mathbf{e}_I \times \mathbf{e}_R| \cdot S_1(t) ds \quad (16)$$

$$L_{path} = \int_C ds \quad (17)$$

The pre-factors $S_{1,max}$ and L_{path} are used for normalisation of the equation for the non-proportionality factor. $\frac{\pi}{2}$ normalises in case that the absolute maximum principal stress describes an ideal circular path.

ANALYSIS OF DIFFERENT STRESS STATES ON THE NON-PROPORTIONALITY FACTORS

In the following, the integral non-proportionality factors described above will be examined with regard to their behaviour under different stress states. For this purpose, a theoretical 2-component stress state according to equation (18) is used.

$$\sigma(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_a \cdot \sin \omega_a t + \sigma_m & \tau_a \cdot \sin(\omega_a t - \Delta\varphi) + \tau_m & 0 \\ \tau_a \cdot \sin(\omega_a t - \Delta\varphi) + \tau_m & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

$\Delta\varphi$ stands for the phase shift between normal and shear stress. For all variations, the influence of individual factors is analysed over a phase range of $\Delta\varphi=[0;\pi]$.

The factors analysed that influence non-proportionality can be divided into the Amplitude ratio V_a , frequency ratio V_f and mean stress ratio $R_{\sigma,\tau}$ (eg. FIGURE 1). For the simplest case, in which only one normal stress and one shear stress are present, the influencing factors are defined as follows:

$$V_a = \frac{\sigma_a}{\tau_a} \quad (19)$$

$$V_f = \frac{f_\sigma}{f_\tau} = \frac{\lambda_\tau}{\lambda_\sigma} \quad (20)$$

$$R_{\sigma,\tau} = \frac{\sigma_m, \tau_m - \sigma_a, \tau_a}{\sigma_m, \tau_m + \sigma_a, \tau_a} \quad (21)$$

As a reference state to analyse each influence the following parameters are set: $V_a=1; V_f=1; R_\sigma=R_\tau=-1$. This allows for an initial test where only the phase shift is of

importance for the non-proportionality. The given non-proportionality factors f_{NP} are shown in FIGURE 2.

All the non-proportionality factors reach their maximum at a phase shift of $\Delta\varphi = 90^\circ$, consistent with literature [7, 17, 18]. The maximum values range from 0.7 to 1. *Bishop, Gaier*, and *Itoh* show a linear increase in the non-proportionality factor initially, while *Bolchoun's* behavior resembles a distribution function. *Bolchoun* underestimates non-proportionality for $\Delta\varphi < \frac{\pi}{8}$ and overestimates it for $\Delta\varphi > \frac{\pi}{4}$, when compared to the other methods. This non-linear behavior is due to the quadratic consideration of the correlation coefficient. *Bolchoun* alone reaches the maximum value of $f_{NP}=1$ for the defined initial state. *Bishop* and *Gaier* do not reach $f_{NP}=1$ because their calculation scales shear stress components, where shear stresses influence the stress course more than normal stress, as detailed in [16].

Below, the individual influencing factors are adjusted in isolation from each other in order to be able to evaluate the individual influences. The variation of the individual components can be seen in Table 1.

The influence of the amplitude ratio is analyzed according to equation (19), varying the normal stress amplitude while keeping the shear stress amplitude

Figure 1: Parameter definition of different parameters: $\Delta\varphi$ phase shift; $\lambda_{\sigma,\tau}$ wavelength; σ_a, τ_a stress amplitude; σ_m, τ_m mean stress.

Figure 2: Non-proportionality factors at different phase shifts for the reference state $V_a=1; V_f=1; R_\sigma=R_\tau=-1$.

Parameter				
Amplitude ratio V_a	0.5	0.75	$\sqrt{2}$	$\sqrt{3}$
Frequency ratio V_f	0.25	0.5	0.75	1.25
Normal Stress ratio R_σ	-0.6	-0.33	0	0.2
Shear Stress ratio R_τ	-0.6	-0.33	0	0.2

Table 1: Parameter set for the analysis of the influencing factors.

Figure 3: Non-proportionality factors at different phase shifts for a variable amplitude ratios.

constant. FIGURE 3 shows the results. For *Bishop*, *Gaier*, and *Itoh*, changing the amplitude ratio scales the non-proportionality values, with the maximum remaining at a phase shift of $\Delta\phi = 90^\circ$. Scaling the normal stress to $\sigma = \sqrt{2} \cdot \tau$ makes the non-proportionality factors for *Bishop* and *Gaier* reach the maximum value of $f_{NP} = 1$. This behavior is linked to the stress tensor definition in R^6 -space. *Itoh* also shows scaling with amplitude ratio changes, but the progression over the phase shift is more linear. If the amplitude ratio exceeds $\sqrt{2}$, the non-proportionality factor decreases, as the normal stress predominates. Unlike the others, *Bolchoun's* non-proportionality remains unchanged with different stress ratios, due to its correlation definition, which evaluates the stress functions independently of the amplitude.

As a second factor the frequency ratio is analyzed according to equation (20) by varying the normal stress frequency while keeping the shear stress frequency constant. FIGURE 4 shows the results. Unlike the amplitude ratio, the frequency ratio significantly affects the non-proportionality course, altering both the magnitude and the maximum position. All factors exhibit

non-proportionality for all phase shifts. For $V_f = 0.5$, the maximum non-proportionality shifts by 90° . *Bolchoun* consistently reaches $f_{NP} = 1$ at certain phase shifts, indicating zero correlation. *Itoh* shows discontinuities at $V_f = 0.25$ due to numerical issues with low frequency causing an open stress path. Similar, but less abrupt, observations occur at $V_f = 0.75$ and $V_f = 1.25$. This issue can be resolved by ensuring closed stress paths in the stress curve.

The influence of the normal stress ratio R_σ , according to Eq. (21), is analyzed with a mean stress applied in addition to the cyclical normal stress. *Bolchoun's* non-proportionality factor shows no dependence on the stress ratio due to its correlation definition. *Bishop* also shows no influence because the mean stress component $\bar{\sigma}$ corrects the stress paths, shifting the tensor path's origin at the mean stress level. In contrast, *Gaier*, who does not correct for mean stress, shows a clear influence, with non-proportionality in the in-phase positions $\Delta\phi = 0^\circ, 180^\circ$. As the stress ratio increases, *Gaier's* non-proportionality rises in the in-phase positions until flattening out between $R_\sigma = -0.33$ and $R_\sigma = 0$. With a further increase in R_σ , f_{NP} is approaching a constant non-

Figure 4: Non-proportionality factors at different phase shifts for a variable frequency ratios.

proportionality level dependent on the mean stress. Itoh also shows dependence on the stress ratio; mean stress in the in-phase position is evaluated as non-proportionality. Unlike *Gaier*, *Itoh* does not reach the initial state's maximum value, and a strong increase in mean stress results in a flatter non-proportionality curve over the phase angle.

Similar behaviour to the normal stress ratio R_σ can be observed for the shear stress ratio R_τ . The non-proportionality factors according to *Bishop* and *Bolchoun* show no change due to an inserted mean stress. *Gaier* and *Itoh* show a decrease in non-proportionality compared to the initial state. For both, the flattening of the curve is significantly faster than for the case of normal mean stress. It can also be observed that the values in in-phase positions are significantly lower than for the normal mean stress. The reason for this behaviour is the scaling of the shear stress in *Gaier* and the influence of the shear stress in the principal stress system in *Itoh*.

To summarize the analysis, the dependence of the stress state on the calculation method used to determine non-proportionality varies. The frequency ratio V_f is the most universally influential factor. *Bolchoun's* non-proportionality factor is the least sensitive due to its correlation definition, disregarding mean stresses and amplitude changes. For a constant frequency, all factors reach maximum non-proportionality at a phase shift of 90° . An amplitude ratio of $\sqrt{2}$ leads to the highest assessment of the damaging effect caused by non-proportional stress, primarily due to the scaling of shear stresses in *Bishop* and *Gaier's* methods. Only *Itoh* and *Gaier* respond to mean stress, detecting non-proportionality at in-phase positions. Beyond a certain stress ratio, the maximum non-proportionality decreases as the mean stress becomes the main component of the stress tensor.

Figure 5: Non-proportionality factors at different phase shifts for a variable normal mean stress ratios.

APPLICATION OF NON-PROPORTIONALITY FACTORS TO SHAFT-HUB PRESS-FITS

The non-proportionality factors will now be applied to a drivetrain, focusing on individually or combined loaded shaft-hub press-fit connections. The interference fit introduces additional normal stress components perpendicular to the surface, leading to a complex three-dimensional stress state within the shaft-hub connection. This is ideal for analyzing the influencing factors.

Three FE models were analyzed to determine the stress tensors: one for the press-fit under pure torsional load, one under rotating bending load, and one under

combined rotating bending-torsional load. Due to the connection's symmetry, a single model is sufficient for the superimposed load to analyze the phase shift between bending and torsional stress. Adjusting the evaluation position on the circumference influences $\Delta\varphi$ by the temporal occurrence of bending stress at the evaluation position.

The models for single loads require evaluation at one critical point, as no additional phase shift between normal and shear stress components occurs. The evaluation zone is located on the shaft side near the hub edge, avoiding the singularity by evaluating a few nodes below the contact zone and axially inside the shaft.

Figure 6: Non-proportionality factors at different phase shifts for a variable shear mean stress ratios

Figure 7: Finite-element model of a shaft-hub press-fit.

FIGURE 7 shows the model structure. Depending on the load, the bending moment M_B , the torque M_T , or both are activated. The hub is fixed at the back. The FE mesh has a fractal-like structure at the contact edge, where the greatest damage is expected. The simulation sequence starts with applying pressure without active friction to minimize introduced shear stresses. After setting the pressure as an interference fit, friction is activated using a simple penalty algorithm. In an intermediate step, the initial bending moment is set for rotating bending, applying bending moments in the x and y directions as opposing sine and cosine functions to simulate the rotating effect. Finally, the other loads (opposing bending component and torsion, if applicable) are applied, matching the fatigue strengths from the respective tests [19].

After completion of the load cycles, the area marked in FIGURE 7 is continuously evaluated for the superimposed load. For the individual loads, only one point in the x - z plane is analysed.

The evaluation begins with an analysis of the stress state, scaling the individual components to the Lamé pressure

$\rho=134$ MPa. FIGURE 8 shows the temporal progression of the stress components for bending (a), torsion (b), and superimposed loads at 0° phase shift (c) and 90° phase shift (d). Additionally, the stress component interactions are presented in matrix form, allowing analysis of the stress paths without scaled shear stresses for the individual components.

As described earlier, the unique feature of contact stress states compared to free surface stress states is the occupancy of the tensor points, which include both cyclic stresses and constant mean stresses in space. Generally, normal mean stresses initially occur on the shaft surface near the hub edge after joining the press fit.

In rotating bending, the stress state is characterized by cyclic components due to stress concentrations at the notch. Initially, pressure intensifies on the bending compression side and diminishes on the opposite

tension side. Axial shear stress arises from friction within the slip zone of the interference fit, its magnitude contingent upon the coefficient of friction.

In pure alternating torsion, normal direction mounting stress remains unaffected. The stress state features two shear stress components: surface shear stress akin to contactless notches and radial-tangential shear stress. Due to the slip condition, the latter does not exhibit a harmonic curve and is "cut off" within the contact area. The plateau height depends on the coefficient of friction, which can vary significantly from its initial value due to minor surface damage in this region.

In simplified terms, it can be concluded that the described stress states of the individual loads are also superimposed for the rotating bending and the alternating torsion (see FIGURE 8). However, additional alternating mechanisms occur, which change the amplitude ratios. These cannot

Figure 8: Transient stresses in shrink fits underneath the contact hub edge; a) rotating bending, b) alternating torsion, c) superposition of rotating bending and torsion at $\varphi = 0^\circ$, d) at $\varphi = 90^\circ$.

	Itoh	Bishop	Gaier	Bolchoun
Bending	0.18	0.07	0.21	0.99
Torsion	0.40	0.33	0.95	0.99
0° combined	0.43	0.07	0.41	0.04
90° combined	0.81	0.88	0.56	1.00

Table 2: Results of non-proportionality factors of uniaxially and multiaxially loaded press fits.

easily be described analytically and depend heavily on the geometric contact design. It can be stated that all components have an oscillating and mean-stress character. The type of load superposition results in a phase shift of the nominal loads over the circumference, as described in detail in [18]. This is also reflected in the local stress in the shear stress component.

The analysis initially shows that non-proportionality is also pronounced for individual loads, depending on the approach. With the exception of *Bolchoun*, low values between $f_{NP} = 0.07 \dots 0.21$ are calculated for pure rotating bending. *Bolchoun* calculates $f_{NP} = 0.99$ as the most damaging effect of the stress state. This may be due to low amplitude oscillation of shear stress components.

In the case of pure torsion, the calculation is divided into two groups. While the approaches according to *Bolchoun* and *Gaier* predict the highest non-proportionality with an almost fully non-proportional stress state, the values according to *Itoh* and *Bishop* are $f_{NP} = 0.33 \dots 0.40$.

When superimposing rotating bending with alternating torsion, the loads are dependent on the circumferential position and thus the phase position. Here, the 90° phase position proves to be the most critical stress state. The calculations result in $f_{NP} = 0.56 \dots 1$. At 0°-phase shift *Itoh* and *Gaier* predict a non-zero non-proportionality of $f_{NP} = 0.41 \dots 0.43$. In contrast, *Bishop* and *Bolchoun* evaluate the stress state at the hub edge as proportional.

SUMMARY – OUTLOOK

The approaches presented here for calculating the non-proportionality of a transient stress state are of great interest for a simple strength assessment. An integration into one of the known strength analyses would enable an estimation of the durability of components without complex numerical investigation of the strength hypotheses. Previous studies on non-proportionality mainly relate to the low cycle fatigue strength and the plane stress state. An analysis of selected calculation approaches for non-proportionality factors (*Bishop*, *Gaier*, *Itoh*, *Bolchoun*) clearly show the influence of the amplitude and frequency ratios as well as the mean stresses on the degree of non-proportionality at different phase shifts of the normal and shear stresses. Qualitatively, all calculation methods show a similar tendency, but quantitatively there are large differences. For example, *Bolchoun* in particular shows major weaknesses in the calculation due to the correlation definition.

For components with contacts, however, analysing the two-dimensional stress state is not sufficient, as a spatial stress state exists at the interface due to the contact pressures applied. In practice, the non-proportional stress states are considered using notch factors, however these have to be determined experimentally by time-consuming model tests. For this reason, the methods of non-proportionality factors were investigated in more detail using a shaft-hub press-fit typical of drive technology. Although *Itoh* shows clear numerical instabilities for frequency deviations, the non-proportionality estimation for the three-dimensional stress space appears to be plausible. *Bishop* seems to underestimate the non-proportionality as he does not consider the mean stress, especially for superimposed loading. But it is not clear, if this effect is already included in the common mean stress consideration in the calculation standards. In contrast, *Gaier* overestimates the influence of the mean contact stress for the load case of pure torsion and underestimates the non-proportionality in the 90° phase shift for combined loading, where the maximum non-proportionality is to be expected.

To summarise, it can be seen that it is still difficult to assess non-proportionality without a strength verification with experimental validation. However, a qualitative assessment using numerical methods appears to make sense in order to check the robustness of existing calculation concepts. Here *Bishop* and *Itoh* show promising results for complex stress states. Further investigations with integration of the non-proportionality factors into a strength verification are being sought after.

LIST OF SYMBOLS

- $a_i \dots$ principle axis of stress tensor
- $b \dots$ second axis of stress tensor
- $e \dots$ Eigenvector of stress tensor
- $f \dots$ frequency
- $f_{NP} \dots$ non-proportionality factor
- $h \dots$ height of enclosure ellipse
- $s \dots$ length between two points in stress space
- $t \dots$ time component
- $w \dots$ width of enclosure ellipse

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x ... stress component in R^6

y ... stress component in $R6$ without mean stress

I ... inertia component

K ... safety factor for multiaxial stress

L ... length of the stress path

M ... integrated correlation value

R ... mean stress ratio

S ... stress tensor/component

α ... material hardening parameter

σ ... normal stress

τ ... shear stress

φ ... phase shift

θ, ψ, ξ ... coordinate angles

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